

Apparent molar volumes of mono- and di-saccharides in water and in aqueous oxalic acid solutions at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K

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Abstract : Apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) have been determined for mono- and di-saccharides, [D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose and sucrose] in water and in aqueous oxalic acid solutions at different concentrations in the range 0.2–1.0 mol kg⁻¹ by measuring the densities at (293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15) K. The limiting apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_{ϕ}) have been obtained in each case and their significance has been discussed briefly. The partial molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^0) have been used to calculate the partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_{ϕ}^0) of mono- and di-saccharides from water to aqueous oxalic acid solutions at different temperatures. The values of limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) and that of $(\partial^2 V_{\phi}^0/\partial T^2)_P$ have been determined from temperature-dependence of V_{ϕ}^0 . It is concluded that all the saccharides behave as structure makers in water as well as in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid.

Keywords : Apparent molar volumes, saccharides, aqueous oxalic acid medium.

Introduction

The thermodynamic properties of carbohydrates are important from biological and technological point of view. The study of saccharides has become the subject of increasing interest because of the multidimensional physical, biochemical and industrially useful properties of these compounds¹⁻⁵. In addition to their importance to the food, pharmaceutical and chemical industries, the simple saccharides have received considerable attention for their ability to protect biological macromolecules⁶. Sugars and polyols are well known stabilizing agents for the native states of proteins/enzymes because of their ability to enhance the structure of water. Various thermodynamic^{5,9-11} and spectroscopic^{12,13a} studies have shown that the hydration of saccharides depends upon the number of hydroxy groups¹³, the potential hydrogen bonding sites and relative position of the next nearest neighbour hydroxy groups within the carbohydrate molecule^{10,14}.

Banipal and co-workers¹⁵⁻¹⁹ have carried out studies relating to the measurement of partial molar volumes of some saccharides in water and in aqueous solutions of urea, guanidine hydrochloride, sodium chloride, cupric chloride and in zinc chloride. In these studies partial molar volume data have been used to calculate partial molar

volumes of transfer (ΔV_{ϕ}^0) for various saccharides from water to aqueous urea/sodium chloride/zinc chloride/guanidine hydrochloride/cupric chloride solutions and the values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 have been rationalized in terms of solute-cosolute interaction.

From the above survey of literature it appears that study in regard to the partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_{ϕ}^0) for mono- and di-saccharides from water to aqueous solutions of oxalic acid, vis-à-vis solute-cosolute interactions are still lacking. With this end in view the title study has been undertaken at different temperatures, viz. 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K to utilise the V_{ϕ}^0 data to determine apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) and the derivative $(\partial^2 V_{\phi}^0/\partial T^2)_P$.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) of glucose, fructose and sucrose in water and in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid have been obtained from the directly determined densities at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K employing the following equation,

$$V_{\phi} = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{m\rho\rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where M is the molecular weight of solute (mono- and di-

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Table 1. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of solutions of glucose as a function of molality at different temperatures in water and in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	$m_s = 0.0$ mol		$m_s = 0.2043$ mol kg ⁻¹		$m_s = 0.4154$ mol kg ⁻¹		$m_s = 0.6309$ mol kg ⁻¹		$m_s = 0.8540$ mol kg ⁻¹		$m_s = 1.0762$ mol kg ⁻¹	
	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V_\phi \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V_\phi \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V_\phi \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V_\phi \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V_\phi \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V_\phi \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)
0.2049	1.0122	110.51	1.0194	104.26	1.0282	104.60	1.0408	106.27	1.0515	106.70	1.0680	110.00
0.3109	1.0191	110.80	1.0269	104.60	1.0356	104.67	1.0478	106.80	1.0581	107.60	1.0744	110.30
0.4193	1.0259	111.10	1.0343	104.95	1.0429	104.80	1.0546	107.40	1.0649	107.90	1.0805	110.80
0.5304	1.0327	111.37	1.0417	105.10	1.0501	105.27	1.0615	107.46	1.0715	108.20	1.0867	111.00
0.6441	1.0396	111.39	1.0489	105.50	1.0574	105.40	1.0683	107.80	1.0776	109.40	1.0930	111.10
0.7609	1.0461	112.00	1.0563	105.50	1.0643	106.00	1.0749	108.28	1.0842	109.40	1.0986	112.00
0.8804	1.0528	112.18	1.0634	105.90	1.0715	106.09	1.0814	108.83	1.0907	109.60	1.1044	112.50
1.0030	1.0594	112.35	1.0707	105.95	1.0786	106.20	1.0881	108.96	1.0965	110.60	1.1091	114.00
1.1290	1.0659	112.67	1.0777	106.40	1.0856	106.51	1.0945	109.40	1.1032	110.40	1.1142	114.83
303.15 K												
0.2055	1.0094	112.00	1.0162	105.76	1.0251	106.40	1.0355	106.71	1.0495	108.60	1.0628	110.90
0.3118	1.0162	112.20	1.0235	105.86	1.0323	106.80	1.0426	106.80	1.0561	109.20	1.0691	111.00
0.4207	1.0229	112.60	1.0309	106.00	1.0394	107.20	1.0496	107.20	1.0626	109.70	1.0751	112.00
0.5321	1.0297	112.60	1.0383	106.00	1.0465	107.20	1.0566	107.20	1.0691	110.00	1.0813	112.10
0.6463	1.0364	112.80	1.0453	106.71	1.0537	107.23	1.0635	107.60	1.0752	110.80	1.0873	112.40
0.7635	1.0430	113.10	1.0528	106.50	1.0600	108.46	1.0704	107.80	1.0816	111.00	1.0928	113.40
0.8834	1.0497	113.10	1.0598	106.90	1.0672	108.31	1.0771	108.14	1.0876	111.60	1.0985	113.90
1.0068	1.0560	113.60	1.0667	107.31	1.0742	108.32	1.0837	108.50	1.0940	111.70	1.1042	114.30
1.1337	1.0622	114.10	1.0736	107.72	1.0813	108.32	1.0904	108.71	1.0996	112.50	1.1095	115.00
313.15 K												
0.2062	1.0058	113.08	1.0121	108.32	1.0201	108.55	1.0285	108.92	1.0439	109.50	1.0574	112.60
0.3130	1.0126	113.27	1.0194	108.32	1.0271	108.69	1.0354	109.08	1.0504	110.00	1.0634	113.20
0.4223	1.0193	113.40	1.0264	108.73	1.0341	108.90	1.0422	109.32	1.0570	110.20	1.0696	113.40
0.5342	1.0260	113.46	1.0335	108.83	1.0411	109.04	1.0493	109.00	1.0633	111.00	1.0752	114.40
0.6489	1.0327	113.60	1.0405	109.13	1.0479	109.49	1.0562	109.14	1.0695	111.60	1.0815	114.00
0.7666	1.0392	113.93	1.0476	109.20	1.0550	109.30	1.0627	109.71	1.0759	111.80	1.0871	114.70
0.8874	1.0457	114.25	1.0545	109.48	1.0616	109.80	1.0692	110.20	1.0824	111.80	1.0924	115.60
1.0111	1.0522	114.40	1.0613	109.73	1.0683	110.19	1.0758	110.50	1.0878	112.90	1.0983	115.60
1.1386	1.0584	114.86	1.0681	110.04	1.0750	110.40	1.0822	110.89	1.0941	113.00	1.1030	116.80
323.15 K												
0.2072	1.0015	114.40	1.0072	110.80	1.0155	111.14	1.0240	111.27	1.0373	111.56	1.0511	113.60
0.3144	1.0082	114.50	1.0141	110.95	1.0223	111.30	1.0307	111.51	1.0437	112.00	1.0572	114.00
0.4243	1.0147	114.85	1.0209	111.47	1.0290	111.80	1.0373	111.80	1.0503	112.07	1.0632	114.40
0.5369	1.0214	114.94	1.0277	111.74	1.0357	111.96	1.0440	111.86	1.0568	112.00	1.0688	115.40
0.6522	1.0280	115.00	1.0346	111.74	1.0425	112.00	1.0506	112.00	1.0631	112.40	1.0748	115.40
0.7704	1.0347	114.94	1.0415	111.84	1.0490	112.40	1.0570	112.40	1.0694	112.80	1.0807	115.60
0.8917	1.0413	115.00	1.0484	111.80	1.0558	112.45	1.0636	112.52	1.0754	113.30	1.0864	116.00
1.0166	1.0474	115.60	1.0552	111.96	1.0624	112.60	1.0699	112.85	1.0817	113.44	1.0920	116.40
1.1446	1.0538	115.80	1.0617	112.37	1.0688	112.86	1.0765	112.93	1.0878	113.70	1.0976	116.70

 m_s = molality of solvent (aqueous solutions of oxalic acid).

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volume, V_{ϕ}^0 and experimental slope (S_V) of aqueous solutions of glucose, fructose and sucrose in water and in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid at different temperatures

Oxalic acid <i>m</i> (mol kg ⁻¹)	$V_{\phi}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)					$S_V \times 10^6$ (m ³ kg mol ⁻²)				
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	333.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	333.15 K
Glucose										
0.0 (water)	110.08 (±0.04)	111.57 (±0.07)	112.60 (±0.07)	114.13 (±0.12)	114.13 (±0.12)	2.32 (±0.10)	2.03 (±0.15)	1.82 (±0.12)	1.31 (±0.18)	1.31 (±0.18)
0.2043	103.94 (±0.05)	105.15 (±0.09)	107.86 (±0.04)	110.68 (±0.12)	110.68 (±0.12)	2.18 (±0.11)	2.12 (±0.19)	1.88 (±0.08)	1.44 (±0.19)	1.44 (±0.19)
0.4154	104.03 (±0.06)	106.11 (±0.13)	108.05 (±0.07)	110.88 (±0.07)	110.88 (±0.07)	2.29 (±0.14)	2.28 (±0.32)	2.04 (±0.14)	1.81 (±0.12)	1.81 (±0.12)
0.6309	105.77 (±0.04)	106.15 (±0.04)	108.25 (±0.12)	110.93 (±0.04)	110.93 (±0.04)	3.38 (±0.15)	2.32 (±0.09)	2.17 (±0.29)	1.85 (±0.08)	1.85 (±0.08)
0.8540	106.19 (±0.08)	107.94 (±0.04)	108.80 (±0.06)	111.06 (±0.07)	111.06 (±0.07)	4.26 (±0.33)	4.18 (±0.17)	3.97 (±0.24)	2.39 (±0.17)	2.39 (±0.17)
1.0762	108.53 (±0.09)	109.82 (±0.04)	111.77 (±0.07)	113.12 (±0.07)	113.12 (±0.07)	5.34 (±0.48)	4.76 (±0.21)	4.32 (±0.32)	3.43 (±0.21)	3.43 (±0.21)
Fructose										
0.0 (water)	111.50 (±0.07)	112.12 (±0.18)	113.09 (±0.14)	113.89 (±0.23)	113.89 (±0.23)	1.31 (±0.09)	1.57 (±0.33)	1.95 (±0.31)	1.14 (±0.36)	1.14 (±0.36)
0.2043	103.70 (±0.07)	104.69 (±0.10)	106.08 (±0.04)	107.37 (±0.06)	107.37 (±0.06)	2.64 (±0.18)	2.37 (±0.26)	1.78 (±0.18)	1.10 (±0.18)	1.10 (±0.18)
0.4154	104.74 (±0.06)	105.15 (±0.05)	106.13 (±0.04)	107.39 (±0.07)	107.39 (±0.07)	2.70 (±0.16)	2.94 (±0.16)	1.86 (±0.08)	1.22 (±0.09)	1.22 (±0.09)
0.6309	106.43 (±0.05)	106.51 (±0.07)	107.16 (±0.07)	107.47 (±0.07)	107.47 (±0.07)	2.87 (±0.16)	3.00 (±0.22)	1.97 (±0.15)	1.64 (±0.10)	1.64 (±0.10)
0.8540	109.45 (±0.03)	110.62 (±0.06)	111.19 (±0.03)	113.26 (±0.04)	113.26 (±0.04)	3.20 (±0.10)	2.96 (±0.19)	2.83 (±0.10)	2.18 (±0.08)	2.18 (±0.08)
1.0762	110.92 (±0.07)	111.65 (±0.02)	112.99 (±0.07)	113.84 (±0.06)	113.84 (±0.06)	3.47 (±0.23)	3.47 (±0.07)	2.86 (±0.22)	2.79 (±0.17)	2.79 (±0.17)
Sucrose										
0.0 (water)	213.84 (±0.15)	215.53 (±0.25)	216.47 (±0.24)	218.23 (±0.27)	218.23 (±0.27)	3.71 (±0.59)	3.28 (±1.06)	3.54 (±1.06)	2.72 (±0.99)	2.72 (±0.99)
0.2043	212.75 (±0.06)	214.33 (±0.08)	214.92 (±0.07)	216.56 (±0.08)	216.56 (±0.08)	2.36 (±0.13)	2.35 (±0.19)	2.04 (±0.15)	1.73 (±0.13)	1.73 (±0.13)
0.4154	213.14 (±0.05)	214.40 (±0.08)	214.99 (±0.07)	216.61 (±0.06)	216.61 (±0.06)	2.43 (±0.13)	2.24 (±0.17)	2.15 (±0.16)	1.74 (±0.11)	1.74 (±0.11)
0.6309	213.52 (±0.07)	214.71 (±0.09)	215.10 (±0.04)	217.15 (±0.06)	217.15 (±0.06)	2.67 (±0.18)	2.43 (±0.24)	2.38 (±0.10)	1.86 (±0.12)	1.86 (±0.12)
0.8540	213.63 (±0.04)	214.96 (±0.07)	215.28 (±0.04)	217.32 (±0.07)	217.32 (±0.07)	2.70 (±0.11)	2.53 (±0.19)	2.44 (±0.10)	2.08 (±0.14)	2.08 (±0.14)
1.0762	213.95 (±0.09)	215.37 (±0.07)	217.01 (±0.06)	218.57 (±0.04)	218.57 (±0.04)	2.97 (±0.28)	2.42 (±0.18)	2.48 (±0.15)	2.18 (±0.08)	2.18 (±0.08)

Standard errors are given to parentheses.

saccharides), m is the molality of the solution, ρ and ρ_0 denote the densities of solution and solvent respectively.

The densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of solutions of glucose, fructose and sucrose in water and in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid have been determined as a function of molality (m) at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K and the representative data in respect of glucose are presented in Table 1. The plots of V_ϕ versus m were found to be linear at different temperatures. The $V_\phi - m$ data were therefore fitted to the following equation,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

where V_ϕ^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume at infinite dilution (which is equal to the partial molar volume of the solute, V_2^0) and S_v is the experimental slope. V_ϕ^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions while S_v is a measure of solute-solute interactions. The parameters V_ϕ^0 and S_v have been evaluated by computerized least-square fitting of $V_\phi - m$ data to eq. (2) and are listed in Table 2 along with standard errors. It is seen that the values of V_ϕ^0 for mono- and di-saccharides are largely positive in water as well as in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid at different temperatures which indicate the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions in solutions of mono- and di-saccharides in water as well as in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid of varying molality (m_s). On the other hand, small values of S_v indicate the presence of weak solute-solute interactions in the solution of mono- and di-saccharides in water and also in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid of varying molality (m_s).

Partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_ϕ^0) of mono- and di-saccharides from water to aqueous solutions of oxalic acid (as solvent) at infinite dilution are calculated from the following equation,

$$\Delta V_\phi^0 = V_\phi^0 (\text{in aq. oxalic acid soln.}) - V_\phi^0 (\text{in water}) \quad (3)$$

The results are presented in Table 3. The parameter, ΔV_ϕ^0

is by definition free from solute-solute interactions and therefore provides information regarding solute-solvent interactions²⁰. A perusal of Table 3 shows that the values of ΔV_ϕ^0 for mono- and di-saccharides are negative in the entire range of temperature investigated. The negative values of ΔV_ϕ^0 may be attributed to an increase in electrostriction in the presence of aqueous solutions of oxalic acid. The electrostriction effect, which brings about shrinkage in the volume of solvent, is increased in the presence of aqueous solutions of oxalic acid as compared to in water.

The variation of ΔV_ϕ^0 with the temperature can be expressed²¹ as below,

$$V_\phi^0 = a_0 + a_1 T + a_2 T^2 \quad (4)$$

The values of coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 have been calculated by least squares fitting of the $V_\phi^0 - T$ data into eq. (4).

The limiting apparent molar expansibilities, ϕ_E^0 have been calculated²¹ from the followings relation

$$\phi_E^0 = (\partial V_\phi^0 / \partial T)_P = a_1 + 2a_2 T \quad (5)$$

The values of ϕ_E^0 for mono- and di-saccharides at different temperatures in water and in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid of varying molality (m_s) are listed in Table 4. A perusal of Table 4 shows that ϕ_E^0 increases with the rise of temperature in aqueous solutions of mono- and di-saccharides in water as well as in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid. This increase in the value of ϕ_E^0 with the rise in temperature may be ascribed to the presence of caging effect²² in relatively concentrated aqueous solutions of oxalic acid.

Hepler²³ has proposed a method by which qualitative information on hydration of solutes can be obtained from thermal expansion of aqueous solution by the following relation,

$$(\partial C_P^0 / \partial P)_T = -T(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P \quad (6)$$

Table 3. Partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_ϕ^0) at infinite dilution of glucose, fructose and sucrose from water to aqueous oxalic acid solutions at different temperatures

Oxalic acid m (mol kg ⁻¹)	$\Delta V_\phi^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)											
	Glucose				Fructose				Sucrose			
	293.15K	303.15K	313.15K	323.15K	293.15K	303.15K	313.15K	323.15K	293.15K	303.15K	313.15K	323.15K
0.2043	-6.14	-6.42	-4.74	-3.45	-7.80	-7.43	-7.01	-6.52	-1.09	-1.20	-1.55	-1.67
0.4154	-6.05	-5.46	-4.55	-3.25	-6.76	-6.97	-6.96	-6.50	-0.70	-1.13	-1.48	-1.62
0.6309	-4.31	-5.42	-4.35	-3.20	-5.07	-5.61	-5.93	-6.42	-0.32	-0.82	-1.37	-1.08
0.8540	-3.89	-3.63	-3.80	-3.07	-2.05	-1.50	-1.90	-0.63	-0.21	-0.57	-1.19	-0.91
1.0762	-1.55	-1.75	-0.83	-1.01	-0.58	-0.47	-0.10	-0.05	0.11	-0.16	0.54	0.34

Table 4. Limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) for glucose, fructose and sucrose in water and in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid at different temperatures

Oxalic acid <i>m</i> (mol kg ⁻¹)	$\phi_E^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)											
	Glucose				Fructose				Sucrose			
	293.15K	303.15K	313.15K	323.15K	293.15K	303.15K	313.15K	323.15K	293.15K	303.15K	313.15K	323.15K
0.0 (water)	0.1288	0.1308	0.1328	0.1348	0.0679	0.0769	0.0859	0.0949	0.1359	0.1394	0.1428	0.1463
0.2043	0.0930	0.1990	0.3050	0.4110	0.1015	0.1165	0.1315	0.1465	0.1157	0.1187	0.1217	0.1247
0.4154	0.1498	0.2123	0.2747	0.3372	0.0256	0.0681	0.1105	0.1530	0.0830	0.1010	0.1190	0.1370
0.6309	-0.0186	0.0379	0.0943	0.1508	0.0204	0.0319	0.0435	0.0550	0.0483	0.0913	0.1343	0.1773
0.8540	0.1246	0.1411	0.1575	0.1740	0.0525	0.0975	0.1425	0.1875	0.0607	0.0962	0.1316	0.1671
1.0762	0.1527	0.1557	0.1587	0.1740	0.0920	0.0980	0.1040	0.1875	0.1445	0.1515	0.1585	0.1671

According to this, the left hand side of the above equation should be positive for all structure breaking solutes and therefore, structure breaking solutes possess negative value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$. On the other hand, positive value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ should be associated with structure making solutes. In the present study the values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ have been obtained from eq. (4) and are listed in Table 5. It is seen that the values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ for mono- and di-saccharides are positive in aqueous solutions and also in aqueous oxalic acid solutions. The positive values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ suggest that mono- and di-saccharides behave as a structure makers in water and also in aqueous solutions of oxalic acid.

Table 5. Values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ for glucose, fructose and sucrose in water and in presence of aqueous solutions of oxalic acid

Oxalic acid <i>m</i> (mol kg ⁻¹)	$(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P \times 10^{12}$ (m ⁶ mol ⁻² K ⁻²)		
	Glucose	Fructose	Sucrose
0.0 (water)	0.0002	0.0009	0.0003
0.2043	0.0080	0.0015	0.0003
0.4154	0.0037	0.00425	0.0018
0.6309	0.0115	0.0012	0.0043
0.8540	0.0025	0.0045	0.0035
1.0762	0.0003	0.0006	0.0007

Experimental

D(+)-Glucose (mol. wt. 180), D(-)-fructose (mol. wt. 180) and sucrose (mol. wt. 342) of purity (99.9%) were E. Merck products. Oxalic acid (dihydrate) (mol. wt. 126) was a B.D.H. product of analytical reagent grade. The water used (specific conductivity $\approx 10^{-6}$ Ω cm⁻¹) in these experiments was deionized and distilled and was degassed prior to making solutions. The solutions were prepared on molality concentration scale using an electronic balance (Mettler) having an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g. Uncertainties in solution concentration were esti-

mated at $\pm 2 \times 10^{-5}$ mol kg⁻¹.

The densities of solutions were measured by using digital vibrating tube densimeter (model 60/602 Anton Parr, Austria). The temperature of the water flowing around the densimeter cell was controlled within ± 0.01 K using an efficient temperature bath. The uncertainties of the density measurements were estimated to be $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ kg m⁻³.

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